

EFFECTS OF WATER UP-TAKE ON INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE PROPERTIES OF VARIOUS CARBON FIBER/EPOXY COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In the case of epoxy resins, moisture has an effect on the mechanical properties of composites. The two materials investigated consisted of thermosetting matrices reinforced with unidirectional continuous carbon fibers. As a result of absorbed moisture, G_{IC} -values increased with the moisture content of the samples, where G_{IIC} -values decreased. It was found that the increase of G_{IC} -values was due to a greater ductility of the matrix and more fiber-bridging which had taken place. On the other hand, interface failure as well as a loss of shear strength of the epoxy were responsible for the decrease in the G_{IIC} -values.

1. INTRODUCTION

Due to the short running resources and environmental preservation, a need exists to save energy in many areas of the every-day life. For moving components, this can be realized in a very efficient way by reducing the weight of the component. That's the reason why not only the aeronautical- and space-travel-industries, but also the automobile and mechanical engineering industries have made great efforts to replace the traditional materials by composites.

Another very important reason for using composite materials consists in the development of engineering which is often restricted due to the properties of conventional materials. Many times, high demands are made to the materials, which cannot always be met by conventional materials. The requested functions can only be fulfilled by combining different, very dissimilar materials. The result of this combination are the composite materials. Especially composite materials made of continuous, orientated reinforcing fibers embedded in a polymer matrix are brought to action in very different fields. These materials are called high performance composite materials.

Composite materials in practical use as structural components can be subjected to a wide variety of different loading conditions. The most important conditions are mechanical stress and environmental attacks. An issue of major concern in the utilization for composites is associated with the occurrence of delaminations or interlaminar cracks, which may be related to manufacturing defects or are induced in service by low velocity impact. Beside the possible influence of temperature, radiation, and exposure to chemicals, the affect of moisture, e.g. atmospheric humidity, must always be taken into account [1].

2. MATERIALS

The two materials investigated consisted of thermosetting matrices reinforced with unidirectional continuous carbon fibers. The resin EP is a epoxy resin of the first generation with a brittle fracture behaviour. It is qualified by a high Young`s modulus, high glass-transition temperature, but a low fracture toughness. The resin EP_{mod} is a matrix of the new generation with a higher strain to failure and a higher fracture toughness. Both materials were cured in an autoclave according to the instructions of the producers. After cutting the edges, the panels were inspected by the Ultrasonic C-scan method, to verify that neither delamination nor an unacceptable high ratio of voids were in the panels. The manufactured laminates produced showed without any exception a very low defect-ratio. The carbon fiber volume fraction was 59±1% for both material systems.

3. TEST PROCEDURES AND DATA REDUCTION

3.1 Moisture Absorbtion

All specimens were dried in an oven at 77°C until their weight loss became stabilized and no further weight loss was observed. After drying, some specimens were tested under dry conditions, other specimens were immersed in hot water. The investigation of the water absorption was performed following the recommendation of the German Standard DIN 53495 [2].

After various periods of time the specimens were taken out of the bath. The weight was measured with an analytic balance and the weight gain was calculated according to following equation:

$$\text{Moisture content} = \frac{\text{weight of specimen} - \text{weight of dry specimen}}{\text{weigth of dry specimen}} \times 100 \quad [\%] \quad (1)$$

The samples absorbed moisture in course of time. After a determined time period, a state of equilibrium was reached. This effect can be explained by the limited solubility of water in the matrix material.

After various periods, the specimens were taken out of the different bathes, were measured and weighed, and than subjected to fracture mechanical tests.

3.2 Mode I and II Tests

Figure 1: Crack opening mode and specimen geometry of the fracture mechanics tests.

For Mode I tests, the double cantilever beam test configuration was used. The mode I tests were performed according to a protocol of the European Group of Fracture [3]. The specimen considered was parallel-sided with a width of 20 mm. In order to initiate a delamination, a film was placed at the laminate's mid-thickness during manufacturing. The loading was introduced via machined loading blocks, which were bonded to the specimen. Loading of the sample took place in a Zwick universal testing machine at a cross head speed of 1 mm/minute. The crack length was measured visually at the specimen's edge, using a travelling microscope. A thin layer of white ink facilitated this measurement. To calculate the critical energy release rate G_{Ic} , the corrected beam theory was used:

$$G_{Ic} = \frac{3P\delta}{2(a+\Delta)B} \quad (2)$$

where P = force, δ = displacement, a = crack length and B = specimen width. The corrected beam theory requires the determination of a correction factor, Δ , to the crack length for taking into account crack-tip rotation and shear deformation. This correction was obtained by plotting compliance to the one-third power, $C^{1/3}$, against crack length a . Δ was the intercept on the x-axis [4].

For the Mode II tests, an ENF-specimen geometry was used. This test is also described in the 'Protocol for Interlaminar Fracture Testing of composites' by the European Group of Fracture. The specimen was loaded in a standard three point bending fixture at a cross head speed of 0.5 mm/min. Due to the bending of the specimen, shear stress was developing in the middle of the specimen. In order to allow a direct comparison of results, the distance between supports, 2L, was fixed at 100 mm. The ratio of crack length was chosen to half span, a/h, equal 0.5. The values of G_{IIC} were calculated from the direct beam theory by using the following expression:

$$G_{IIC} = \frac{9a^2P\delta}{2B(2L^3+3a^3)} \quad (3)$$

The individual parameters of this equation were already explained above.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Moisture Absorbtion

The samples were rested in water bathes of three different temperatures: 23, 70 and 100°C. For both materials the weight approached a constant saturation level. The maximum moisture content of CF/EP and CF/EPmod were 1.6 and 2.5 weight percent, respectively. The higher the bath temperature, the faster the specimens absorbed moisture, and the faster the curve was approaching the equilibrium state.

Figure 2: Moisture absorbtion behavior at different temperatures of the materials tested.

The CF/EP_{mod} material at 100°C is forming an exception. The moisture absorption curve of this material is decreasing after passing a maximum. Literature sources in which similar phenomena have been observed [5], explain this behavior depending on micro cracks appearing in the material due to the humid and hot environment. This enables water to rapidly enter the material and to produce a fast gain of weight. Because of the growth of these micro cracks and due to the detachment of fibers and matrix, small matrix pieces break off the material, causing a loss of material and a reduction of the total weight of the specimen.

4.2 Interlaminar Fracture Tests

The variation of G_{IC} as a function of moisture content is shown in Fig. 3. Mode I values of CF/EP_{mod} are much higher than those of CF/EP, but CF/EP gets a bit more tougher with increasing moisture content than the modified epoxy. The G_{IC} -values of CF/EP_{mod} versus moisture content exhibit an unusual course, because of a decreasing of the G_{IC} -values of about 8%, which could be observed for samples be rested in boiling water until they reached half of the saturation. After that, the G_{IC} -values increased till the saturation was reached. Therefore the average of the G_{IC} -values at the end was about 15% higher than the one measured in dry conditions. This behavior can be explained by investigating the fracture surfaces using scanning electron microscopy. The decrease of the G_{IC} -values for short immersion times was a result of the fact, that, on the one hand, the matrix was not tough enough yet, and on the other hand, the moisture had already damaged the interface. The further increase of G_{IC} -values was found to be due to a larger plastification of the matrix, resulting from the moisture absorbed, and hence more energy consumptive fiber-bridging effects. For the more brittle material CF/EP, an increasing of the G_{IC} -values was visible with an increasing moisture content right from beginning (by about 64%, with a scatter of 6%).

Figure 3: Results of the mode I tests versus moisture content.

Figure 4: Results of the mode II tests versus moisture content.

Mode II delamination fracture toughness, G_{IIc} , is shown in Fig. 4 as a function of moisture content. For both materials, it can be seen that the G_{IIc} -values decrease with increasing moisture content. The average values of G_{IIc} of the saturated CF/EP_{mod} specimens decrease by about 12% in comparison to the dry specimens, and the scatter is about 7%. For the CF/EP, a decrease of 7% can be found, at a scatter of 6%. The reduction of the G_{IIc} -values is a result of weakening of the interface as a consequence of the absorbed moisture. Fracture surfaces of dry specimens show extensive hackling, whereas the saturated specimens show less hackling and a lot of bare fibers.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The major objective of this investigation was the evaluation of changes in fracture mechanical behavior due to absorbed moisture. Two different types of materials were tested, a brittle and a modified epoxy matrix, both reinforced with carbon fibers. Specimens that had been immersed in water showed some increase in G_{IC} . This increase in G_{IC} is the result of plastification of the matrix due to moisture absorption. The reduction in shear fracture toughness, G_{IIc} , was caused by a greater weakening of the fiber/matrix interface. The increase in matrix plastification did not play an important role in this case.

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